

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: JACKSON-FORBES****FIRST NAME: PHILIPPA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. When writing a paper, students should practice five rules of thumb which are:
 - Stay focused, write clearly, support assertions, do not make the writing boring and clumsy, and do not plagiarise.¹**
 - Do not plagiarise, know when the paper is due, write the essay from beginning to end in a single study session, do not lose track of the question, and stay focused.
 - Do not submit the essay after the paper is due, start each sentence with the subject, do not use an apostrophe in adjectival phrases, do not plagiarise, and stay focused.
 - Write clearly, do not plagiarise, stay focused, know when the paper is due, and start each sentence with the subject.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 12–14.

2. What is Plagiarism, and why should the source be mentioned?
- Plagiarism is taking an author's copyright without asking for permission. Researchers mention the source when the author grants permission.
 - Plagiarism is stealing and using information not purchased from the author. Researchers mention the source because plagiarism is wrong.
 - Plagiarism occurs when a writer uses a source of information but does not give credit to the author of the information source. Researchers mention the source because plagiarism is wrong, unethical, and a serious offence.²**
 - Plagiarism is when a writer uses an information source but does not give credit to that source. Researchers mention the source because it is unethical to steal.
3. To make a research topic manageable, students should question their topic and evaluate their questions. Students should avoid questions with answers that would be merely speculative. All except one of the instances below apply. Select the inapplicable one.
- Questions with answers that are dead ends.
 - Questions with answers that are not settled facts that someone could quickly look up.³**
 - Questions with answers that require different capacities from the ones a student has.
 - Questions with answers that researchers are unable to disprove plausibly.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 34.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed., Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 27–28.

4. Quoting, paraphrasing, and summarising appropriately are critical for drafting the research paper. Which one of the answers best describes when students should quote?
- The paragraph's content can be included in the research.
 - The words are from an article in a magazine.
 - The words are original and refer to one of the concepts in the research.
 - The words express a claim that the student disagrees with; to be fair, the student wants to state it precisely.⁴**
5. Sources should be evaluated for relevance and reliability. Which of the answers best describes how to evaluate sources' relevance quickly?
- When the source is a book, skim the first and last paragraphs in the chapters that use many of the student's keywords.⁵**
 - When the source is a journal article, read the first and last paragraphs of the chapters.
 - Skim the sections labelled bibliography and appendices when it is an online source.
 - If the source is a book, check the headings in the table of contents for the layout of the chapters.
6. Citations are required when compiling the research paper. Therefore, students should be cognisant of when to include a source citation. Which of the choices below differs from the source information researchers should include in the citation?

⁴ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 77.

⁵ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 41.

- Who wrote, edited, and translated the text?
 - The citation style used, i.e., notes-bibliography style or author-date style.⁶**
 - The title and subtitle of the work; volume number, edition number, or other identifying information; and page numbers.
 - Who published the text, and what was the date when the author did it?
7. The literature review gives a detailed and critical review of the literature that is the foundation for dissertation research. Which of the following helps ensure the literature review has a proper foundation?
- Researchers should ensure that they clearly define all terminology for the reader to clarify anything confusing.
 - Structure the paragraphs to appropriately build the argument for asking the research questions.
 - Ensure that each paragraph has a strong topic sentence. Students should include transition sentences between main topics.
 - All of the above.⁷**
8. Validity refers to how much an instrument measures what it is supposed to measure. Which of the following statements on validity is true?

⁶ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 140.

⁷ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee, FL: Educational Psychology and Learning Systems Faculty Publications, 2017), 31–32.

- Evidence for factorial validity is not included in the professional manual for the measure and is derived from criterion validity studies.
 - Construct validity is concerned with the congruence between how someone builds the instrument or test and the conceptual or theoretical basis of the instrument.
 - Face Validity refers to evidence that researchers secure via individual interviews and focus groups that are part of the development of the measure.⁸**
 - Discriminant Validity is also called diverse validity and is concerned with the validity of questionnaires and observations.
9. The limitations of the study discuss the unexpected circumstances that hinder or disrupt the interpretation of the research findings. Which statement on limitations is false?
- Limitations in the data analysis result when many test subjects are biased.⁹**
 - Limitations in sampling refer to unforeseen difficulty in obtaining a sufficiently large number of subjects resulting in a limit on the generalisability of the findings.
 - An example of a limitation in the measure is when a measure that usually demonstrates sound reliability malfunctions making it difficult to test hypotheses.
 - Limitations in the treatment refer to unforeseen difficulty in utilising the techniques used in delivering the treatment in the research design.
10. For the methodology and research approach, theoretical information is required to answer the research question. It sheds light on the problem that students are

⁸ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 40–41.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 59–60.

investigating. They can also assess the known information on the topic of inquiry.

Which of the following is not a benefit of theoretical information?

- Provide support for the analysis, interpretation, and synthesis.
- Support and provide evidence for the methodological approach.
- Provide support for conclusions drawn, and recommendations suggested.
- Provide methodology for the research questions that form the conceptual framework's development and refinement.¹⁰**

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 446–447.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.